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Ordering chaos: the fractal as the geometry of infinity through art and computer graphics

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Resumo

Que papel desempenha a confluência da computação e dos fractais na criação artística contemporânea? Nesta proposta, pretendemos refletir a influência do desenvolvimento da computação gráfica na compreensão e representação do fractal e como este é utilizado no panorama artístico atual. Observaremos a evolução do conhecimento dos fractais através de autores que explicam os aspectos matemáticos como é caso do Mandelbrot (1982) e estéticos como é caso do van Den Boom e Tejedor (1998), que nos darão as chaves para compreender o impacto que a simbiose desta geometria e da computação provocou na cultura. Através da obra de Julius Horsthuis, Michael Hansmeyer e Iris van Herpen, observaremos a ligação entre o material e o virtual e como se desenvolvem imaginários que perspectivam um futuro onde a natureza se funde com a tecnologia e a arte.

Palavras-chave: Geometria Fractal; Computação Gráfica; Pós-Humanismo; Natureza.

Abstract

What role does the confluence of computer science and fractals play in contemporary artistic creation? In this proposal, we intend to reflect on the influence of the development of computer graphics on the understanding and representation of the fractal and how it is used in the current artistic panorama. We will look at the evolution of knowledge of fractals through authors who explain the mathematical aspects, such as Mandelbrot (1982), and the aesthetic aspects, such as van Den Boom and Tejedor (1998), which will give us the keys to understanding the impact that the symbiosis of this geometry and computing has had on culture. Through the work of Julius Horsthuis, Michael Hansmeyer and Iris van Herpen, we will see the connection between the material and the virtual and how imaginaries develop that envisage a future where nature merges with technology and art.

Keywords: Fractal Geometry; Computer Graphics; Posthumanism; Nature.

INTRODUCTION

In this article we will look at how fractal geometry and its application through computation allows us to explore utopian, post-humanist worlds and create a new imaginary through technology.

Fractal geometry emerges as another way of seeing and understanding the structures of

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nature (MANDELBROT, 1982), but also to reproduce it and apply its peculiarities to art (VAN DEN BOOM; ROMERO TEJEDOR, 1998), creating new aesthetics and movements such as *Fractal Art* (MITCHELL, 1999). Understanding its main characteristics is essential to understand how artists such as Leonardo da Vinci or Maurits Cornelis Escher bring them closer through repetition and scale variation.

Subsequently, we will analyse how the development of computing has been indispensable for the knowledge and application of fractal geometry in other fields such as medicine and economics.

Finally, we will focus on analysing the work of three artists who use fractal geometry through computation to create pieces that take us to futuristic, imaginary worlds, where the organic is complemented by the artificial, generating new aesthetics and possibilities regarding how our future may look. We will see the application of parametric programmes to immersive installation by Julius Horsthuis, fashion design with 3D printing by Iris van Herpen and the application of algorithms to architectural construction by Michael Hansmeyer.

FRACTALS

The term "fractal" was coined in 1975 by the computer scientist and mathematician Benoit Mandelbrot, who defined all those "rough, brittle" structures that we could find in nature, those that, due to their geometry, were considered "monsters" by Euclidean geometry.

La matemática clásica está enraizada en las estructuras regulares de la geometría de Euclides y en la evolución continua característica de la dinámica de Newton. La matemática moderna empezó con la teoría de conjuntos de Cantor y la curva de Peano que lleva el plano. Desde el punto de vista histórico, la revolución se produjo al descubrirse estructuras matemáticas que no encajaban en los patrones de Euclides y Newton. Estas nuevas estructuras fueron consideradas... "patológicas", ... como "una galería de monstruos", emparentadas con la pintura cubista y música atonal, que por aquella época trastornaron las pautas establecidas en el gusto artístico. (MANDELBROT, 1982, p.18)¹

¹ Classical mathematics is rooted in the regular structures of Euclid's geometry and the continuous evolution characteristic of Newton's dynamics. Modern mathematics began with Cantor's set theory and the Peano curve that

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Therefore, fractal geometry has a series of specific characteristics that differ from Euclidean geometry, giving answers and meaning to many remote forms such as the branching of trees, the coastline or the nerves of leaves.

Fractal structures can be found at different scales, either through a microscope or a telescope, so we could say that they go beyond scale. Their proportions are maintained, and the form is repeated towards infinity, so that, with a single fragment, we would understand the totality of the structure. “The importance of fractals may lie in the fact that, by knowing a small part of them, it is possible to reconstruct their whole structure, since they are a self-similar pattern that repeats itself at different scales” (RIVERA, LÓPEZ, 2012 p.123).

Fractals are self-similar; therefore, they can be found at any scale and their structure does not vary according to size. They are constantly repeating, following the principle of homothety, which is the geometric relationship established between two shapes which maintain the same proportion since their points are aligned to a fixed one. Fractals can "grow" inwards (internal homothety) or outwards (external homothety). The next feature that differentiates fractal structures is the fractal dimension.

The fractal dimension was developed by the physicist Felix Hausdorff in 1919 and improved by the Ukrainian mathematician Abram Samoilovich Besicovich, which establishes the level of roughness of an element, so that no matter what scale we are at, the level will be the same. The fractal dimension is bound to the topological dimension of the structure, which is usually larger. “A fractal is, by definition, a set whose Hausdorff-Besicovitch dimension is strictly greater than its topological dimension” (MANDELROT, 1982, p.32). And, finally, we have a characteristic that we have already discussed above with respect to self-similarity and homothety, but which is important with respect to the subject that concerns us, which is **infinity**. Fractal sets can repeat themselves, starting from the principle of homothety up to infinity, but not

carries the plane. From a historical point of view, the revolution occurred when mathematical structures were discovered that did not fit the patterns of Euclid and Newton. These new structures were considered ‘pathological’, ... as ‘a gallery of monsters’, related to cubist painting and atonal music, which at that time upset the established patterns of artistic taste. (MANDELROT, 1982, p.18)

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without being influenced by chance.

In nature, chance is an important aspect in the development of fractal structures. Benoit Mandelbrot develops this concept further in *Fractal: Form, Chance and Dimension* (1977) where he explains that chance acts on fractal objects regardless of their scale: "... internal homothety makes randomness equally important at all scales, so that it makes no sense to talk about macroscopic and microscopic levels" (MANDELBROT, 1984, p.52).

Mathematicians such as Robert Koch, Waclaw Sierpinski and Gaston Julia investigated these phenomena and began to develop equations that allowed the realisation of fractal sets. These authors, however, did not yet have computers that would allow them to infinitely iterate these formulas.

FRACTAL AESTHETICS

Throughout history we have been able to see how mathematics and art have been inseparable disciplines, since, among other things, beauty resided in proportion, so it was essential to use geometry and mathematics to create aesthetically attractive and absorbing pieces.

Authors such as Leonardo da Vinci, Albrecht Dürer and others have been clear examples of this phenomenon, and in the search for and understanding of the forms of nature. Mandelbrot already mentions some examples in which the fractal has been represented in art, clearly not knowing the term, but we can observe in works such as *The Great Wave of Kanagawa* (1831) or Leonardo da Vinci's *Flood* (1480) how there is an intention to represent the repetitive structures of the forms of nature.

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Fig 1 - THE GREAT WAVE OF KANAGAWA Katsushika Hokusai.1831. Xylographic print,25 cm × 37 cm.

At the end of the 20th century, along with the appearance of computers and information technology, aesthetics and artistic manifestations based on fractal geometry have been appearing. An example of this can be found in the book by Holger van den Boom and Felicidad Romero Tejedor in *Fractal art: aesthetics of localism* (1998) in which he develops a relationship between the fractal and a way of creating works of art, calling it "local aesthetics". Local aesthetics is based on the idea of generating pieces starting from one or more points on the support and the elements grow around them, without a previous sketch, reminiscent of the growth of trees, for example. Homothety manifests itself in the construction of the work together with self-similarity. "It was not enough for Matisse to describe nature; he had to 'create' it anew each time. Matisse would do what for Picasso it was to place one object next to another." (VAN DEN BOOM, ROMERO TEJEDOR, 1998, p.73)

In 1999 appears *The Fractal art manifesto*, a manifesto by Kenry Mitchell that established a basis for what fractal art was, and what it was not. This movement focused more on the use of the computer for the realisation of fractal images, in which they stood out for their great colour.

Fractal is not (...) Something that anyone with a computer can do well. Anyone can pick up a camera and take a snapshot. However, not just anyone can be an Ansel Adams or an Annie Liebovitz. Anyone can take brush in hand and paint. However, not just anyone can be a Georgia O'Keeffe or a Pablo Picasso. Indeed, anyone with a computer can create fractal images, but not just anyone will excel at creating Fractal Art. (MITCHELL, 1999)

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There were artistic manifestations that wanted to approximate these characteristics of the structures of nature. Fractal geometry was also used in famous architectures such as the Sagrada Familia in Barcelona (HERRERA, SAMPER,2015) among others. Escher, inspired by the tesserae of the Alhambra (LÓPEZ, LÓPEZ, LÓPEZ, LÓPEZ,2003,p.37-62) made a series of drawings and engravings in which he repeated a specific shape, even using millimetric feathers to give a greater sensation of depth. However, no matter how hard he tried, Escher could not capture infinity. Infinity was made possible by the development of computers.

THE ARRIVAL OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

As we have already mentioned, before the development of computers, some mathematicians began to propose geometric forms with which the structures of nature could be ordered. However, something was wrong with them: they could not iterate the equations forever, so their geometries lacked an essential ingredient in the fractal: **infinity**.

In the 1970s Mandelbrot was working at IBM. He was interested in fractals and one day he decided to enter Julia's equation into an IBM 1401 computer and iterate the equation infinitely and translate those numbers into colours. This gave rise to the famous Julia Set. This was a turning point in the understanding of the structures of nature, fractal geometry was related to Chaos Theory and new ways of doing things appeared.

The 'amorphous', irregular, strange, came to make sense and to have an order. However, Mandelbrot himself stated that he was not able to classify many of the fractal sets. "Some fractal sets are curves or surfaces, others are unconnected 'powders', and there are also those with such ludicrous shapes that I have not found, neither in science nor in the arts, words that could describe them well" (MANDELBROT,1982, p.15).

APPLICATION OF FRACTALS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

The introduction of fractal geometry in computing meant a before and after in the way

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nature was interpreted, but also in other aspects of the science and culture of the time.

On an aesthetic and design level, fractal patterns expanded, creating merchandising and new ways of designing fashion, such as Jhane Barnes (1954), a fashion designer who hired a physicist and mathematician to create a specific programme to generate fractal patterns from parameters.² In the scientific field we can find that fractal geometry can be used to detect cancer before a tumour develops. Research led by Igor Sokolov (Tufts University) and Craig Woodworth (Clarkson University) studied the presence of fractal geometry in human cells during their conversion to cancer³. While the relationship between fractal and cancer has been previously mentioned and demonstrated at a macro scale, this study showed that at the nano scale, this connection may be more complicated as it arises specifically at one stage of cancer development. In geography, fractal geometry is a very interesting tool for establishing the roughness of a terrain, its irregularities. There are many programmes, such as FROG V2, developed by the researcher Jean-François Parrot, which determines the fractal dimension of objects from images and using different procedures, calculates the parameters and produces a final report.⁴

Another relationship is fractal geometry and economics. The graphs that show the rise and fall of the stock market can behave in a similar way to fractals, so it is possible to predict how it will continue, although it is not an exact science.

In the audiovisual field, fractals soon found their way into the limelight. In the film *Star Wars: Episode III - Revenge of the Sith* (2005), fractal geometry was used in the visual effects, making, for example, the movement of the lava more interesting and believable.

² ASPELL, P. (Executive Producer) JERSEY, B. (Director) SCHWARZ, M. (Director) *Hunting the Hidden Dimension* (Season 35, episode 14) [Chapter of a TV series]. Quest Productions (Production company) Kikim Media (Production company) associated with The Caticus Corporation. 2008.

³ DOKUKIN, M. E. Emergence of fractal geometry on the surface of human cervical epithelial cells during progression towards cancer. *New Journal of Physics*. vol 17, 2015.

⁴ Parrot, Jean-François. (2013). *Manual de utilización del Software FROG V2 (Fractal Research On Geosciences, Versión 2.0)*. p.3

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Fig 2 - *Frame of Star Wars: Episode III-Revenge of the Sith*(2005).

Source:

<https://rpp.pe/videojuegos/geek/star-wars-francia-reconoce-el-duelo-con-sables-laser-como-un-deporte-oficial-noticia-1181624>

As we have seen, there are many programmes designed for various fields of science and design. Nowadays, we can find several fractal parametric programs, many of them free, that allow us to create fractal structures in 2D and 3D, make renders and animations. These programmes are very interesting tools for use in the field of design and art.

One of the most well-known and recommended programmes is MandelBulb 3D, a parametric 3D fractal programme that allows you to make infinite combinations, iterations, modify the colour and lights of the fractal piece and render them to later create an animation. With the rise of immersive installations and VR, more and more artists are opting for this type of programme to create hypnotic virtual scenarios, such as Julius Horsthuis, for example.

JULIUS HORSTHUIS

Julius Horsthuis (Amsterdam, 1980) is a digital artist who uses the MandelBulb 3D program along with other editing and effects programs such as After Effects to create audiovisual pieces for immersive installations, music videos or VR among others. He started his career as a visual effects specialist and worked on music videos for big artists such as Avicii and Lady Gaga. He discovered his interest in fractals which, together with his skills in visual effects, led him to make pieces that he discovered his interest in fractals which, together with his visual effects skills, led him to create pieces that gradually spread to galleries and museums such as the Nxt Museum in Amsterdam and Hangar Y in Meudon. His pieces incite the observation of every detail, how the

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fractal columns expand, grow, and disappear at the same time as other structures appear, expanding towards infinity, enveloping the spectator, and making him dream of utopian, strange, different worlds, where nature merges with technology and the environment becomes fantastic.

Fig 3 - *Foreign nature at Nxt Museum* (Julius Horsthuis, 2022)
Source: <https://www.julius-horsthuis.com/immersive-installations#/foreign-nature-1/>

IRIS VAN HERPEN

Iris Van Herpen (Wamel, 1984) is a haute couture designer who draws inspiration from the forms of nature to create unique pieces through modulation. Her work combines multidisciplinary technologies and craftsmanship, employing pioneering techniques with luxurious materials. One of his most outstanding works is his 3D TOP CR0152 (Capriole Collection, 2011), made in collaboration with the architect Isaïe Bloch. This modular piece is made in 3D printing, the shapes are repeated by increasing and reducing their size, being self-similar. 3D printing allows the most interesting proposals from the virtual field to be brought more flexibly into the realm of reality, encouraging creativity and the birth of new imaginaries.

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Fig 4 - 3D TOP CR0152. Iris Van Herpen and Isaïe Boch. 2011.3D Print. Horsthuis, 2022)
Source: <https://archimorph.com/2012/08/07/climatically-responsive-clothing/>

MICHAEL HANSMEYER

Michael Hansmeyer (Germany, 1973) is an architect and programmer who explores the use of algorithms in the creation of architectural pieces. His work often combines generative and CAD programs in which he virtually creates these works, many of them using fractal geometry, which he eventually brings to reality through 3D printing. Among other works, Hansmeyer used this method to create a set design for a theatrical performance of the Magic Flute (2019), in which we can see how symmetrically distributed organic forms have been generated, reminiscent of baroque altarpieces, inviting classical works to merge with new imaginaries through technology. He is currently working on Torre Blanca (Tor Alva), which, at 30 metres high, will be the tallest 3D printed structure in the world. This is possible thanks to the modular construction that has allowed the tower to be built in parts that form a structure of branching columns.

Fig 5: *Simulation of Tor Alva* (ETH Zurich, Hansmeyer and Dillenburger, 2024.)
Source: <https://www.michael-hansmeyer.com/white-tower>

CONCLUSION

As we have seen throughout this article, the connection between fractal geometry and computation has allowed us to develop new aesthetic trends and ways of perceiving and

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understanding our world. Computation has allowed us to represent infinity through numbers, to imagine diverse possibilities through art and design, fusing technology and nature. These symbioses allow us to be inspired and create new ways of expressing ourselves and interpreting our environment.

Therefore, it is interesting to let new technologies continue to advance, as we do not know what they may hold for us or what we may discover through them.

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